

Scanning Buyer's Awareness of
Traditional E-commerce and Dropshipping and Measuring
their Satisfaction Level: **An Empirical Study of Nepalese
Perspective**

by

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Abstract:

This study explores the levels of consumer awareness, satisfaction, and loyalty in relation to traditional e-commerce and dropshipping within the Nepalese context. Given the accelerating adoption of online commerce and the increasing inclination of Nepalese youth toward dropshipping as an entrepreneurial avenue, the research seeks to delineate key differences in consumer perceptions and experiences between these two models. A quantitative research design was employed, utilizing primary data gathered through an online survey comprising 104 respondents. Statistical analyses—including descriptive statistics, independent sample t-tests, and linear regression—were conducted using SPSS to assess the impact of perceived service quality, perceived value, and perceived risk on customer satisfaction and subsequent loyalty.

The results indicate that while general awareness of dropshipping is notably high, consumer satisfaction and loyalty toward dropshipping platforms remain markedly lower than those observed in traditional e-commerce. Dropshipping is frequently associated with greater perceived risk and reduced service quality, both of which appear to undermine customer trust. Conversely, traditional e-commerce demonstrates comparatively higher satisfaction and repurchase intention among users.

The findings affirm the hypotheses that customer satisfaction significantly contributes to loyalty, and that perceived value positively—while perceived risk negatively—influences consumer loyalty across both models. This study fills a notable gap in the existing literature on dropshipping in Nepal and provides practical implications for improving customer-oriented strategies in emerging e-commerce ventures.

Keywords: *E-commerce, dropshipping, Nepal, customer satisfaction, consumer behavior, loyalty, Business Transformation, SMEs.*

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Chapter 1.

Introduction

Setting the Stage (Exploring the Research Problems and Objectives)

In the contemporary digital transformation era, one of the revolutionary industries that changed the dynamics of how businesses operate globally is e-commerce. The global market value of the **e-commerce market is \$16.6 Trillion, as of 2022** (IMARC Group, 2023). E-commerce can take various forms, but one of the newest and fastest-growing forms of e-commerce is 'Dropshipping'. Dropshipping has gained popularity and has become a means for many young entrepreneurs to make money. Many youngsters are dropping off their education and seeking another way of income by escaping the 'ordinary nine to five job', and are involved in Dropshipping (Majid, 2020). The global market value of **dropshipping was \$ 225.99 billion with a forecasted CAGR of 27.1% from 2022 to 2031** (Grand View Research , 2022), (Allied Market Research, 2022).

There is the ease of doing business with dropshipping as in it, there are lower capital investments in terms of inventory as well as logistics. Since, dropshipping involves retailers selling their products to customers, by further passing the sales order to suppliers (third-party), making the supplier responsible for the shipment of products directly to the customers. Hence, **dropshippers forfeit some control over customer experience**. Additionally, there are major setbacks in the dropshipping industry that hinder its growth, including security in terms of **payments, difficulties in product shipments, and logistics**. Along with the growth of e-commerce, there are many factors that propel the dropshipping market, including e-commerce sectors' retail sales, fiber connections in different countries, and internet usage. For instance, in the global context, according to UNCTAD (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development), **retail sales in e-commerce increased from 16% to 19% in 2020** (UNCTAD, n.d.). As well as, as of 2020, according to (OECD, 2023) major countries including, Chile, Austria, the UK, Israel, and Belgium expanded their fiber connection by a significant account of 50%.

In the Nepalese context, the revenue of the e-commerce market is **\$ 1,134 million as of 2023** (Statista, 2023). Even the **average revenue per user (ARPU)** is expected to be an amount of **\$80.23**, which is a great indicator of the growth of the e-commerce landscape in Nepal. These data are relevant to our study because the growth of e-commerce is directly proportional to the growth of dropshipping. But with an increase and scope in dropshipping, it is very important to have studies based on customer

satisfaction and loyalty related to dropshipping but there exist severe problems. Let us discuss it briefly:

1.1 Harmed Customers

As of January 2022, with a **market penetration rate of 38.4%**, Nepal has seen a significant increase in its internet users. As **11.51 million users** are the contemporary scenario of its trending landscape, the e-commerce industry is booming with a scope of blossoming in the coming days as the number of online users increases along with the market penetration rate (Timilsina, 2023). With the increase in e-commerce trading, there is a rise in Dropshipping. But these drop shippers often sell products directly from **suppliers such as AliExpress, Shopify, JINGYI, EC21**, etc.

The dropshippers' main aim is to create a website, including marketing the product or goods as their own product, they also design advertisements on Instagram, Facebook, etc., that end-users see. Imagine paying Rs 1,500 for a basketball from an advertisement recommended by Facebook, to eventually find that same article on AliExpress for Rs 800. This is an experience for many Dropshipping customers, as it is shallow for the drop shippers to let their customers believe that the product is their own brand and set up a markup price so high (Jinqiong Lei, 2022). Additionally, there is the **rise of import of goods in Nepal, which is leading to a drain of foreign exchange reserves**, which creates **pressure on the balance of payment, further leading to currency depletion**. Hence, as per the latest restrictions, Nepal is banning on import of 10 goods items **as foreign exchange reserves dwindle** (The Kathmandu Post, 2022).

1.2 Severity of the Problem

On a global level, there are many news articles that discuss the topic related of unsatisfied customers related to dropshipping (see for instance (Hedges, 2018)). But there are not many studies or surveys or even any study material that exists, in the context of Nepal. Many people, majorly youth are investing a lot of money into Dropshipping, they risk their future by dropping out of their education to pursue this. Even, though many entrepreneurs are turning towards digitalization and being part of e-commerce, **there exists a huge research gap that needs to be addressed in order to understand Dropshipping and compare it with traditional e-commerce**. This will give us insight into the contemporary scenario of general demographics, concerning their experience with e-commerce as well as Dropshipping. Because on the other hand, in an international scenario, there are customers that feel Dropshipping did not reach their expectations.

1.3 Problem Statement

“Do the customer satisfaction and loyalty levels differentiate between Dropshipping and traditional E-commerce, in the context of Nepal?”

1.4 Research Questions

- 1. Are Nepalese aware of the differences between dropshipping and traditional e-commerce?*
- 2. How does customer satisfaction differ between Dropshipping and traditional E-commerce in Nepal?*
- 3. What are the factors that influence customer loyalty in Dropshipping as opposed to traditional E-commerce in Nepal?*
- 4. Do customer satisfaction lead to customer loyalty?*

1.5 Aims and Objectives

The main aim of this report is to find the different levels of outcomes from dropshipping and traditional e-commerce and are the customer satisfaction level and ultimately loyalty different if we compare both with each other.

1.5.1 Specific Achievable

- To find if customer satisfaction and loyalty correlated with each other and can customer satisfaction lead to customer loyalty.
- To find the customer satisfaction level of dropshipping clients and traditional e-commerce clients.

1.6 Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Customer Satisfaction positively influences customer loyalty toward both traditional e-commerce and dropshipping.

Hypothesis 2: Perceived Value positively influences customer loyalty toward both traditional e-commerce and dropshipping.

Hypothesis 3: Perceived Risk negatively influences customer loyalty toward both traditional e-commerce and dropshipping.

1.7 Limitations

This paper will discuss the emergence of Dropshipping, and address the research gap that exists in the market of Nepal, by relating to the differences between traditional e-commerce and Dropshipping which will include the major difference in the way these businesses manage their **logistics and inventory**. Therefore, some of the limitations that the survey might have been are, **time limitations factors not taken into account**, because of the complexity of the measurement. Additionally, since the survey in the report will be distributed among people through social media channels, there is a chance that most of the **responses could be from the same age, language, and equal-minded. Hence, leading to lower representativity of the results.**

Chapter 2.

Literature Review

Unboxing Insights: A Comprehensive Review

Theories and Concepts Used

1. Quality-Satisfaction-Loyalty (QSL) paradigm
2. Perceived risk-value Model
2. EC-SERVQUAL model
3. Service-Dominant Logic
4. Expectancy-Disconfirmation Model
- 5.

2.1 Traditional E-commerce

E-commerce, often regarded as electronic commerce can be defined as utilizing electronic media and the Internet in order to deal with goods and services (Vipin Jain, 2021). In traditional e-commerce, the seller, after receiving an order, is responsible for shipping the products to the customers (E S Soegoto, 2018). Particularly, the seller in this model holds an inventory of its own. The main characteristic of this model is that sellers have to buy their inventory in bulk, in regards to selling at a markup to its provided customers.

2.2 Dropshipping

According to marketing literature, Dropshipping is determined as a marketing function in which the physical goods as in inventory sidestep intermediaries, while the name is through all the concerned parties (Israfilzade, 2017). The underlying function includes both the supplier that provides goods by filing the order for the e-tailor and the retailer that orders. Hence, the highlight of Dropshipping is that, unlike traditional e-commerce, the seller orders the required products from suppliers and does not necessarily purchase and store inventory, leading to no investment in inventory upfront including no need to manage inventory systems and levels as well as warehouse space (Faiza Renaldi, 2020).

For instance, according to a study by (Store Leads, 2023), one of the major suppliers of dropshipping is 'Shopify', let us analyze the **growth of Shopify in Nepal**:

- **Quarter-over-quarter in Q1 of 2023, Shopify stores in Nepal increased by 15.0%.**
- **Year-over-year in Q1 of 2023, Shopify stores in Nepal increased by 48%.**

This graph signifies the cumulative growth of Shopify stores in Nepal by Quarter:

Additionally, (Store Leads, 2023) showcased top shipping carriers for the Shopify stores are:

- **1.5% shipped by USPS,**
- **0.8% shipped by DHL,**
- **0.8% shipped by FedEx.**

Shipping Carrier	Stores
USPS	2
DHL	1
FedEx	1
Royal Mail	1

Figure 1: Cumulative Shopify Stores by Quarter in Nepal

Let us also list social media usage on Shopify stores, according to (Store Leads, 2023):

- **42.3% of stores use Instagram in Nepal.**
- **40.8% of stores use Facebook in Nepal.**
- **10.8% of stores use YouTube in Nepal**

The most significant difference between traditional e-commerce and Dropshipping is **logistics-affiliated management**. The reason is that a drop-shipper is an intermediary between suppliers and end-users. Even though Dropshipping is just another form of e-commerce and both have a similar way of doing business, there have been many reports and news suggesting unsatisfied and unhappy Dropshipping customers (see for instance Appendix 1, 2, and 3).

2.3 QSL (Quality-Satisfaction-Loyalty) Chain

According to (Olsen, 2002), one of the major predictors of customer satisfaction is quality, which also arbitrates the relationship of **quality-loyalty**. For instance, empirical studies (Joo, 2008) demonstrated that product or service quality in any industry has an impact on customer satisfaction, which is directly **correlated to customer loyalty**, hence, supporting (Olsen, 2002). In this research paper, the chain of QSL will be divided into the following sections, for ease of understanding:

- **Perceived e-service Quality,**
- **Customer Satisfaction,**
- **Customer Loyalty.**

2.3.1 Perceived e-service Quality

Already existing works of literature that have studied the quality in the arena of e-commerce use service quality as a reference or starting point (see for instance (van Iwaarden, 2004)). E-service quality can be defined, in the words of (Parasuraman, 1988) as, the extent to which any web-related subjects facilitate services that include the delivery of products, shopping, and purchasing, effectively as well as efficiently. However, if we need to study the quality of e-commerce, we cannot apply it like the traditional quality (service) dimension. Therefore, in order to access the customers' perception of a website, whether it be of dropshipping or traditional e-commerce, we need to adopt what is known as the **EC-SERVQUAL model**, proposed by (Chang, 2008).

2.3.2 Customer Satisfaction

A key metric that is used to measure the level of satisfaction of the associated customer with regard to the products or services provided by the business (Ain Damia Zamry, 2020). The concept of customer satisfaction is based on and analyzed on the basis of various research as well as a thesis. One such instance can be related to conducting surveys or feedback. These collected data can be used to analyze and identify areas of improvement (Nurnatasha Mohd Yusoff, 2020). In other words, **customers that are satisfied are potential loyal customers**, impacting the long-term relationships between customers and businesses. The reason is, the value is often equal to **perceived service quality relative to customer acquisition costs and price** (Blanchard, 1994).

2.3.3 Customer Loyalty

The concept of a loyal customer can be associated with the key driver of a business's success (Elina Närvänen, 2020). Since they are individuals or entities that have regular purchases from a specific business over an extended period of time, organizations often maintain customer loyalty through various strategies that include **loyalty programs, consistent customer service, and personalized marketing** (Tamilla Curtis, 2011). Overall, customers that are loyal are regarded as assets to the company. A few of the highlights of loyal customers are:

- Result in an **increase** in sales,
- Leads to an **increase** in profit,
- Further leads to a **decrease** in price sensitivity,
- Resulting in **increased** word-of-mouth marketing.

In this study, we **focus on attitudinal loyalty**, as well as in this report we will regard customers' loyalty as their commitment to making **repeated purchases** as well as **disseminate position WOM** (Word-of-Mouth).

2.4 Perceived Risk-Value Model (extrinsic cue-quality-risk-value)

There is multiple perceived risk-value model, but for the purpose of this paper, the model proposed by (Agarwal, 2001) will be used as it is useful to practitioners because it shows the relationship between marketers' and consumers' **perception of risk**. It also provides insight that can be helpful to marketers in order to enhance the perceived value. The relationship between extrinsic cues and perceived risk is arbitrated by the perceived quality and is consistent with the **extrinsic cue-quality-risk-value paradigm**.

There are two types of cues or factors that come into play when consumers seek information from sources. These cues are **intrinsic and extrinsic** cues. Customers may take decisions on purchasing on the basis of extrinsic stimuli such as word-of-mouth, price, brand image, name, and advertising. According to (Murray, 1991), in terms of reducing the 'perceived risk', word-of-mouth is the most effective source of information. Hence, for this study, we focus on the extrinsic cue of **word-of-mouth (WOM)** as well as the perceived-risk-value model is divided into the following parts:

2.4.1 Extrinsic Cue: eWOM (Electronic Word-of-Mouth)

An empirical study by (Hennig-Thurau, 2003) demonstrated that eWOM is the factor affecting the consumption experience by customers and circumstances whether it be current, former, or potential enunciations (e.g., **comments, replies, opinions**) whether it be negative or positive. **eWOM** can take various forms including blogs, communities, reviews, websites or discussion forums, etc.

In previous marketing studies, **eWOM** is regarded as an exogenous variable that is independent and often is developed only with respect to its dependent variables. This helps to specify dimensions of WOM that are context-specific (Hennig-Thurau, 2003). Hence, in the current study, the development of **eWOM** measures are motives that are theoretically driven and include perceived e-service quality and risk.

2.4.2 Perceived Risk

If we define, perceived risk, in the words of (Bauer, 1967) as, a **subjective belief** from the perspective of the consumer about the **negative outcomes** that can be potentially uncertain and often related to possible online transactions. (Bhatnagar A., 2004) proposed that there is major two types of perceived risk, namely, **privacy and performance**. When products' performance or functionality are being concerned by the end-user regarding the failure of it to meet the expectation, it is regarded as a performance risk. Whereas, privacy risk is related to security and related to negative association with online behavior of purchasing. In this paper, as we mentioned, perceived risk will be based on two factors, i.e., **performance risk and privacy risk**.

2.4.3 Perceived Value

(Parasuraman, 2000) demonstrated that the consumers' perception of what is received against what is given and the concluded overall assessment of the utility of the products or services is **perceived value**. Hence, this paper will also regard **perceived value** as defined by (Parasuraman, 1988). Since, the empirical study done by (Keeney, 1999) also defines it as the benefits that the consumers receive against the commodity or monetary instrument provided as well as the sacrifices incurred during the delivery of that particular product or service.

With the emergence of hype of Dropshipping, is there any customer base, that drop shipper can build, that are satisfied and remains loyal in Nepal? If there exists such a customer base, is it more engaged as it is with traditional e-commerce, in the context of Nepal? The purpose of this report is to explore these questions.

2.5 Perceptual Framework

There are three independent variables that are introduced to be studied as a reference to already existing research papers and empirical studies, these could impact the dependent variables.

Hypotheses	Prior Literature	Remarks
Customer Satisfaction	(Chen, 2012)	According to this paper, one of the strongest predictors 'customer trust and loyalty' is minor against customer satisfaction , especially in, the e-commerce industry regarding B2C. Additionally, this research concluded that customer satisfaction and customer loyalty are positively and directly correlated with each other.
Perceived Value	(Kuo, 2009)	This research concluded that there exists a correlation between the high level of service quality offered/ high value and the high level of customer satisfaction.
Perceived Risk	(Sweeney, 1999)	This research suggests that consumer take few uncertain costs and perceived value when they perceive low level of risk associated with the transaction.

Chapter 3.

Research Methodology

Decoding the Methodology Process and Implementation

In this chapter, we will be dealing with the primary data collection and different approaches. We will be briefly discussing each of them:

3.1 Research Philosophy

A set of beliefs, values, or even assumptions that are taken under a research process is known as research philosophy. In the words of (Mauthner, 2020) undertaking any research, the necessary presumptions or approaches taken to understand certain areas is called research philosophy. There are two major assumptions in research philosophy, namely, **ontology** and **epistemology**.

- **Ontology** deals with the fundamental assumptions that the researcher takes to investigate a particular problem related to research and often is related to the belief of the researcher about the nature of a particular subject (Berryman, 2019). From an **ontological stance**, particularly from this paper suggests that 'reality differs from each individual'.
- Whereas, **epistemology**, explores three dimensions of the study of knowledge that include how the particular subject is acquired, organized, and applied. From an epistemological stance, the researcher while investigating a subject acquire the knowledge of how it is to be obtained and judges if the knowledge can be considered reliable or valid (Marilyn M. Rawnsley, 1998). Specifically, in this paper, the epistemological stance is to get concrete information and data using statistical tools.

These were the philosophical assumptions, but there also exist research philosophies, that include, **positivism, critical realism, interpretivism, postmodernism, and pragmatism** (Otieno, 2020). But, for this paper, taking into consideration our ontological and epistemological stance, the best-suited research philosophy is the 'Pragmatism Approach'. As pragmatism approach enables us to take into consideration of both qualitative and quantitative methods.

3.2 Research Methods

As (Stephen J. Gentles, 2016) explains the two types of research methods, include the quantitative method and the qualitative method. Let's discuss each of them briefly:

- **Quantitative Methods:** In this method, researchers collect experiences, and views and sometimes collect data regarding the behavior on a particular topic.

This method provides an investigation that provides an in-depth understanding of the problems that exist (Corte, 2019). This type of method uses structured surveys, experiments to collect data, or simply questionnaires. This method also investigates the complexity of the subject by studying variables, ultimately helping to obtain outcomes of the specific issue

- **Qualitative Methods:** This method majorly focuses on non-numerical data to draw a conclusion, this includes text, pictures, and observations that is solely focused on understanding by providing open-ended questions for its observation (Apuke, 2017).

The current study is based mainly on the '**Quantitative Method**', as it will help us better understand the level of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty with regard to dropshipping against traditional e-commerce. We will also be using statistical tools on surveyed data in order to convert the results into a rational outcome.

3.3 Data Collection

The process of gathering data and information regarding research, which includes data from different sources and is used to further analyze and make decisions accordingly is called data collection (Elise Paradis, 2016). The process of data collection includes:

- **Identifying data and information sources,**
- **Stating data collection methods designs,**
- **Collection of data.**

There are two types of data collection, primary research, and secondary research, let us discuss each briefly:

- I. Primary Research: Also known as original research, on the basis of contemporary information, the act of collecting the data is primary research (OSWEGO, 2023). The aim is to conduct surveys and helps researchers to answer their queries regarding any subject that has not been researched before. There are many forms of primary research, some are surveys, interviews, etc. The primary data for this paper is been collected through an online survey. A survey form was designed in Google Form, which gave us the reliability from respondents as they could all access it. A sample size of 110 is taken for this study, as convenience samples.
- II. Secondary Research: When the researchers base their study on the basis of an already published study, paper, research work, journal article, or credible documentation of any sort, it is known as secondary research (Martins, 2018). We have used, journal articles, books, and articles in a periodical as our secondary research.

3.4 Research Approach and Design

For this paper, we will be using the **deductive approach**, as it provides us the major advantage of starting with theory or rather say hypotheses and further testing it with empirical observations in order to analyze the data and come to a specific conclusion (Jaana Woiceshyn, 2018). This approach will provide us with information and data on a certain subject or problem and the researcher then presumes hypotheses. This is very different from the **inductive approach**, in that the researcher has to collect the data of related subjects first and then come up with theories and further analyze them (Thomas, 2006).

3.5 Survey Design

The survey design of an empirical study is very important. As we already selected our approach, i.e., quantitative approach, now we will be choosing either analytical or descriptive. Both the survey design has its own advantages, let us discuss that briefly:

- **Analytical Survey:** Helps establish cause and effect relationship, eliminates extraneous variables, helpful to determine the effectiveness of interventions or treatments.
- **Descriptive Survey:** Helpful in a broader understanding of the sample size, helps to identify patterns in data, and assists in gathering information regarding opinions, attitudes, or behaviors.

For the current study, we will be using a descriptive survey that will include, **closed-ended questions** with a variety of **multiple-choice questions**, a **5-point Likert scale**, and **dichotomous questions**.

3.6 Analytical Method

As we discussed earlier, there are three variables and hypotheses stated, which include consumer satisfaction, perceived value, and perceived risk. For the purpose of data analysis, we will be using **IBM SPSS** in order to rationalize the quantitative data, solely driven by convenience, reliability, and ease of use (Arifa Rahman, 2021).

The other aspect of the analytical method is '**Hypothesis Testing**'. It is a technique that is used to evaluate where the proposed hypotheses of a particular subject regarding a particular population are supported by the sample of available sample. For this current paper, we will be using the Pearson Correlation Coefficient, wherein the size of the value range is set between +1 to -1 (Schober, et al., 2018).

3.7 Customer Satisfaction

We have included dichotomous questions as well as **5-Point Likert Scale** (ranging 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). The variables of customer satisfaction were measured with this scale of (Setó-Pamies, 2012).

3.8 Customer Loyalty

We used Dichotomous question regarding the loyalty of the customers as customer satisfaction might not always lead to customer loyalty. Most of the question include 'yes', 'maybe' and 'no' as the answer.

Chapter 4.

Data Presentation and Analysis:

Crunching the Numbers: Revealing the Insight

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

A total of 104 responses were recorded from the survey we conducted. Here are the results from the survey:

4.1.1 Age Group

The pie-chart above showcases the age group of the respondents. The survey had a diversity in the age group as it contained participation from all age groups. The majority of the respondents were from the age group **(18-24) with 30.8%**, followed by age group **(25-34) accounting for 24%** and the age group **(35-44) accounting for 17.3%** then the age group **(Under 18) accounting for 13.5%** as well as **55 and above accounting for 7.7%** and lastly the least participation of **45-54 accounting for 6.7%**. Here, the maximum participant signifies the **rising level of awareness in the youth of Nepal**.

4.1.1 Gender

Our survey consisted of various gender including male, female, and anonymous, signifying the inclusiveness in our survey. Wherein, majority of the demographics were **female accounting for 43.3%**, followed by **male accounting for 38.5%** and **18.3% of**

anonymous responds. This graph dictates the involvement of **female as active users of online purchasing activities**, whether it be dropshipping or traditional e-commerce.

4.1.2 What is the highest level of education you have completed?

The chart above dictates the most respondents have a **Bachelor's Degree as they accounted for 41.3%** of all and least where of **Doctorate or higher-level accounting for 13.5%**. This signifies the majority of the online product purchasing users are mostly educated.

4.1.3 Have you ever purchased anything online?

Most of the respondents had **purchased online as they accounted for 98.1%** with only exceptionally few people not ever using internet to buy **products/services that is 1.9%**.

4.1.4 If you answered yes to the previous question, how often do you purchase items online?

Maximum respondents that **had purchased online were once a month accounting for 28.4%** and least of **‘once a week’ and ‘more than once a week’**. This data signifies majority of respondents buy most of products online, showcasing **the increase in reliability in e-service**.

4.1.5 Have you ever purchased anything from a traditional e-commerce store?

96.2% of the respondents had been involved in using e-commerce (traditional). This signifies that traditional e-commerce has reached to most demographics of Nepal.

4.1.6 If you answered yes to the previous question, how satisfied were you with your experience of purchasing from a traditional e-commerce store?

5-Point Likert Scale in this question signifies that **74.3% of the respondents were really satisfied from traditional e-commerce**. Additionally, **22.8% of the respondents moderately satisfied** and **only 2% not satisfied**.

4.1.7 Are you aware about the term 'Dropshipping'?

The fact that **96.2% of the general population of Nepal being aware about 'Dropshipping'** signifies the level of awareness about this subject making it easy for us to determine the awareness and further the awareness about the difference between traditional e-commerce and dropshipping.

4.1.8 Are you aware of the differences between Traditional E-commerce and Dropshipping?

Since, earlier the data showed 96.2% of people being aware about dropshipping, **94.2% of people, according to this data, states that they are aware about the differences between traditional e-commerce and dropshipping.** This data is important further in the conclusion as it helps us in the investigation of the level of satisfaction and loyalty that might differ between the two.

4.1.9 Have you ever purchased anything from a Dropshipping store?

Only 8.7% of our respondents said that they have not ever purchased from the dropshipping store. This signifies the growth of e-commerce in Nepalese context as well as how people now are transforming their lives and embedding e-service into their lives. This data showcases that we can now further compare the satisfaction level of consumers that might differ.

4.1.10 If you answered yes to the previous question, how satisfied were you with your experience of purchasing from a Dropshipping store?

This data is very important for our paper, as it showcases how majority of the respondents are not satisfied from dropshipping as only **1% where fully satisfied** and majority of individual, that is, **75.5% of respondents very dissatisfied from dropshipping stores.**

4.1.1 Do you perceive, there are risk associated with dropshipping?

This data shows that **98.1% of the respondents feel there is risk associated with ordering from dropshipping.** This data signifies the perceived risk and how it influences the customer satisfaction and loyalty.

4.1.2 To what extent do you agree with these statements?

On the basis of average answer, let us construct average responses of these statements:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I find Dropshipping more convenient than traditional e-commerce	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I trust traditional e-commerce more than dropshipping	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I believe dropshipping provides better prices compared to traditional e-commerce	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am satisfied with my experience of purchasing from traditional e-commerce	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
I would purchase from a dropshipping store again in the future	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I would purchase from a traditional e-commerce store again in the future	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

4.1.3 If you had to choose between purchasing from a traditional e-commerce store and a Dropshipping store, which one would you choose?

10.7% of the people described that their decision of choosing between traditional e-commerce and dropshipping will depend upon the product. Whereas, 89.3% would choose traditional e-commerce rather than dropshipping stores.

4.1.4 Did your satisfaction with your purchase from a Dropshipping store lead you to make another purchase from the same store?

This pie-chart represent the customer loyalty of dropshipping consumers. As we can observe, **13.7% of respondents were uncertain about them choosing dropshipping as their next action.** Most importantly, **81.4% of the respondents where not loyal to dropshipping.**

4.1.5 Did your satisfaction with your purchase from a traditional e-commerce store lead you to make another purchase from the same store?

This graph showcases that traditional e-commerce is the mainstream e-service that people of Nepal would choose rather than any other form. Traditional e-commerce is much prevalent in the contemporary scenario of business. As **98.1% of the respondents are loyal to this service, and 1.9% being uncertain.**

4.2 Inferential Analysis

Average customer satisfaction of Dropshipping is calculated as follows:

Independent Variables	I am very satisfied with the dropshipping stores	I find dropshipping more convenient than traditional e-commerce	I believe dropshipping provides better prices as compared to traditional e-commerce	Mean Customer Satisfaction of Dropshipping Store
Mean	4.710	5.000	4.840	4.852
Std. Deviation	1.362	1.305	1.387	1.210

Average customer satisfaction of traditional e-commerce is calculated as follows:

Independent Variables	I am very satisfied with the traditional e-commerce	I find traditional e-commerce more convenient than dropshipping	I believe traditional e-commerce provides better prices as compared to dropshipping	Mean Customer Satisfaction of traditional e-commerce
Mean	5.29	5.33	5.43	5.348
Std. Deviation	1.276	1.369	1.271	1.131

Independent sample T-test customer satisfaction of dropshipping and traditional e-commerce:

Particulars	df	Significance (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
Equal Variance Assumed	228	0.0001	0.591

4.3 Linear Regression

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficient (β)	Coefficient standard error	Significance (p)
Mean customer satisfaction of Dropshipping	0.695	0.087	0***
Age	0.019	0.011	0.100
Gender	0.069	0.190	0.716
Education level	-0.145	0.083	0.085
Survey	0.047	0.214	0.826
R Square	0.427		

*Dependent Variable: Mean customer loyalty of Dropshipping. *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001*

As we refer to the scatterplot and P-P plot (provided in Appendix 3), we can notice that there exists no clear pattern as well as the data is distributed randomly. Therefore, this indicates the assumption of homoscedasticity and linearity are met. In the case of traditional dropshipping the effect of customer satisfaction on customer loyalty has observed to be greater (β is 0.620). Additionally, the customer satisfaction of traditional e-commerce on customer satisfaction of dropshipping store are significant. This has been observed since, $p(0) < \alpha(0.05)$. Furthermore, the R square of the total model is 0.454, this indicates that independent variables does not analyses and discusses the variation of dependent variables.

Chapter 5.

Summary, Conclusion and Implications

From Insight to Action: Interpreting the Result

5.1 Summary of Results

We can confidently say that the results of the survey indicated that the customer experienced a much higher level of satisfaction and as satisfaction is directly proportional to loyalty, higher level of customer loyalty for traditional e-commerce, in the context of Nepal. We can also now predict that the general level (average) of satisfaction in dropshipping faced backlash and received negative media attention (some studies support this as well, such as (Emerce Legal, 2020) and (DUIVENVOORDEN, 2020)).

Even, the results of control variables, as mentioned before, that include age, level of education, age, and experiment had an effect on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. One of the major similarities between the linear progression of both 'dropshipping' and 'traditional e-commerce' was a similar unstandardized coefficient (B) in terms of satisfaction of customers. This made it difficult for us to investigate the effects of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty dropshipping or traditional e-commerce, the reason being the significance of both and equally big data.

Synopsis

This study is in line with all the previous literature works that had already shown that customer satisfaction level affects loyalty as well. After the mandatory use of multiple-choice questions, dichotomous questions, and the 5-Point Likert Scale, we can conclude that the results of this paper show a positive correlation between customer satisfaction, and perceived value influences customer loyalty toward both traditional e-commerce and dropshipping and negatively influenced by perceived risk, in context of Nepal.

5.2 Implications

As, this study is contributing towards academic literature regarding the topic of Dropshipping in Nepal, by establishing knowledge on the subject matter. We had found literature paper, see for instance (Themistocleous, 2020) on the subject of the relationship between customer loyalty and satisfaction, this paper is focused on expanding the young field of knowledge, especially in context of Nepal. The conclusions from this paper signified the superiority of traditional e-commerce from dropshipping in context of satisfaction and loyalty of customers. Previously published literatures made it clear that customer satisfaction is positively correlated to customer loyalty. This fact is also backed up, from the conclusions of our survey. Since, we know that customer loyalty and profit are directly proportional to each other, we can say that, dropshipping stores and businesses should work on increasing the level of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty to further generate profits and expanding their business (Beeker, 2021).

Appendices

Appendix 1: Questions from the Survey

Scanning Buyer's Awareness of Traditional E-commerce and Dropshipping and Measuring their Satisfaction Level: An Empirical Study of Nepalese Perspective

The survey consists of a series of questions that will help us understand your demographics, your experience with online shopping, your preferences towards e-commerce and dropshipping, and your satisfaction and loyalty towards these modes of shopping.

The survey will take approximately *10-15 minutes* to complete, and your responses will be kept confidential. Please answer all questions truthfully to the best of your knowledge.

Data gathered from this survey will be used for academic purposes only, and we appreciate your participation in this study.

Thank you for your valuable time and inputs.

Rhythm Singh,

Isha Bajgain,

Umesh Prasad Yadav,

Laxmi Shrestha.

What is your age?

- Under 18
- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55 and above

What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say

What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- High school or less
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctorate or higher

Have you ever purchased anything online?

- Yes
- No

If you answered yes to the previous question, how often do you purchase items online?

- Less than once a month
- Once a month
- 2-3 times a month
- Once a week
- More than once a week

Have you ever purchased anything from a traditional e-commerce store?

- Yes
- No

If you answered yes to the previous question, how satisfied were you with your experience of purchasing from a traditional e-commerce store?

	1	2	3	4	5	
Very dissatisfied	<input type="radio"/>	Very satisfied				

Are you aware about the term 'Dropshipping'?

- Yes
- No

Are you aware of the differences between Traditional E-commerce and Dropshipping?

- Yes
- Maybe
- No

Have you ever purchased anything from a Dropshipping store?

- Yes
- Maybe
- No

If you answered yes to the previous question, how satisfied were you with your experience of purchasing from a Dropshipping store?

	1	2	3	4	5	
Very dissatisfied	<input type="radio"/>	Very satisfied				

To what extent do you agree with these statements?

Strongly disagr... Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I find Dropshipping more convenient than traditional e-commerce	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I trust traditional e-commerce more than dropshipping	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I believe dropshipping provides better prices compared to traditional e-commerce	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am satisfied with my experience of purchasing from traditional e-commerce	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
I am satisfied with my experience of purchasing from a dropshipping store	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
I would purchase from a dropshipping store again in the future	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I would purchase from a traditional e-commerce store again in the future	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

If you had to choose between purchasing from a traditional e-commerce store and a Dropshipping store, which one would you choose?

- Traditional E-commerce Store
- Dropshipping Store
- It depends on the product

Did your satisfaction with your purchase from a Dropshipping store lead you to make another purchase from the same store?

- Yes
- Maybe
- No

Did your satisfaction with your purchase from a traditional e-commerce store lead you to make another purchase from the same store?

- Yes
- Maybe
- No

Appendix 2: Responses Recorded

Appendix 3: Assumptions of Linear Regression in Dropshipping

Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

Scatterplot

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